

Music, Mind, Body and Brain - Music Battery (MMBB-MB): A Multidimensional and Mobile-Compatible Assessment of Music-Related Behavior

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Abstract

The measurement of music-related behavior has historically been fragmented, with existing instruments tending to isolate individual facets of music cognition, such as melodic perception, rhythmic processing, or emotional response. These instruments have also typically been restricted to narrow age ranges or specific clinical populations. We present the Music, Mind, Body and Brain Battery (MMBB-MB), a cross-sectional tool designed to assess auditory, motor, cognitive, emotional, and social aspects of music-related behavior concurrently and across the lifespan, in both healthy and clinical groups. The battery comprises six sub-batteries: Perception & Memory, Rhythm, Movement, Singing, Emotion, and Music Experience—of which four are original tasks and two are adapted from established instruments. By assessing multiple domains simultaneously, the MMBB-MB enables the investigation of relationships that have been difficult to examine previously, such as the covariation between rhythmic perception and motor synchronization, or between emotional responsiveness and social engagement with music. The battery was implemented using jsPsych, with a particular emphasis on mobile compatibility, leveraging smartphone accelerometer and gyroscope sensors to capture whole-body movement remotely. This online architecture increases accessibility and ecological validity and supports large-scale, cross-cultural data collection, while remaining compatible with controlled laboratory protocols.

1. Background

Measurements are fundamental to scientific inquiry. In the field of music psychology, a central challenge is determining how to measure an individual's capacity to perceive, produce,

and appreciate music. Standardized research tools began to emerge in the beginning of the 20th century, when Carl Seashore proposed a test to quantify perceptual constructs such as pitch and rhythm discrimination (Seashore et al., 1956). This was followed by Gordon's Musical Aptitude Profile (1965), which aimed to measure the potential to learn music, rather than current musical skill. Other tests of music-related behavior were developed as diagnostic tools, such as the Montreal Battery of Evaluation of Amusia (MBEA), although this has seen use with healthy participants as well (Peretz, 2003). Over the ensuing decades, a vast array of psychometric tests measuring different aspects of music behavior and cognition have been developed and validated (e.g., Müllensiefen et al., 2014; Law & Zentner, 2012; Wallentin et al., 2010; Iversen & Patel, 2010; Ullén et al., 2014).

As is common with many other fields of science, the study of music has been carried out from a rather fragmented perspective, due to complexity of music-related behavior and cognitive processes. Features such as spectral and temporal content, as well as emotional, motor and societal impacts have mostly been addressed in isolation, and in narrow age groups or clinical populations. As a consequence, prevailing models separately target single facets of music cognition, such as melodic perception (Narmour, 1990), rhythm and metric perception (Vuust & Witek, 2014), musical emotions (Juslin & Sloboda, 2001), resulting in a constrained perspective that lacks cohesion between different aspects of music.

The Music, Mind, Body and Brain Musical Battery (MMBB-MB, Figure 1) is proposed as a cross-sectional measurement tool, which targets auditory, motor, cognitive, emotional and social aspects of music throughout every stage of life (childhood, adolescence, adulthood, late adulthood). It is suitable for both healthy individuals and populations with psychiatric, developmental, or neurological conditions. Beyond targeting different populations, MMBB-MB enables the assessment of multiple domains of music behaviour simultaneously, rather than in isolation. For example, the battery allows researchers to examine whether rhythmic perception covaries with motor synchronization, whether singing accuracy relates to perceptual pitch discrimination, or whether emotional responsiveness predicts social engagement with music.

The MMBB-MB was also designed to be an asset for naturalistic and cross-cultural music research. Traditionally, studies have been conducted in the laboratory, with artificial musical stimuli that are specifically composed to test a narrow set of hypotheses. In addition, participant samples are heavily biased in terms of geographic and socio-economic background (Henrich et al., 2010; Jacoby et al., 2020). The MMBB-MB addresses these issues by providing a set of sub-batteries that can be administered online, with minimal geographical limitations, and that require only access to the internet and a smartphone. Our tasks are designed to be compatible with highly controlled laboratorial settings, where researchers can combine MMBB-MB with high end measurement systems such as motion capture and electroencephalography (EEG).

FIGURE 1. Interface of the MMBB-MB online implementation.

2. MMBB-MB

a. Target music behaviors and structure of the battery

The MMBB-MB is divided into six tasks (Table 1), namely 1) Perception & Memory, 2) Rhythm, 3) Movement, 4) Singing, 5) Emotion, and 6) Music Experience. The Perception & Memory sub-battery targets the perception of spectral (pitch, melody) and temporal (rhythm, beat) features, as well as melodic memory. The Rhythm sub-battery focuses on temporal processing and sensory–motor synchronization at the level of discrete motor actions. The Movement sub-battery extends the assessment of sensory–motor synchronization to continuous whole-body movement. The Singing sub-battery targets vocal–motor production, including pitch and temporal control. The Emotion sub-battery assesses musical emotion recognition and perception, while the Music Experience sub-battery captures subjective musical experiences, including musical training and hobby background, genre preferences, emotion and reward functions, and subjective musical skills. Out of all sub-batteries, MMBB-MB includes four original tasks and two tasks adapted from previous literature.

Table 1 - General description of MMBB-MB sub-batteries. Total durations include the sum of all trials, plus an estimated time for reading the instructions.

Sub-battery	Trial descriptions	Original	Total duration (minutes)
Rhythm Tapping	Unpaced tapping; Metronome; Music	Yes	5
Beat Alignment	Beat alignment of one training trial and 6 songs		12
Movement	Unpaced walking, bouncing to metronome; Free dance to researcher selected stimulus; Free dance to self-selected stimulus	Yes	15
Perception & Memory	2-alternative forced choice tasks where individuals indicate whether or not two melodies are the same (perception), or if they have heard it before (memory)	No	18
Emotion Recognition	2-alternative forced choice trials. Participants choose the emotion the music expresses most from two options	Yes	5
Ratings	Participants listen to a track and provide ratings of valence, arousal, and liking		
Music Experience	Participants read and respond to questionnaires.	No	15
Singing	Singing single tones, short tone sequences, familiar song and novel song	Yes	15

b. Implementation and ecological validity

Following current trends in psychology research (Correia et al., 2022; Reips, 2021; Gagné & Franzen, 2023), a special focus is given on mobile compatibility of MMBB-MB, which increases accessibility and privacy, whilst reducing constraints of time, cost, and geographical barriers. In addition, remote experiments offer increased ecological validity by capturing responses in participants' natural environments. Finally, most mobile phones are nowadays equipped with high quality sensors, which enables the administration of paradigms such as the one we proposed for the Movement sub-battery (Table 13, Section 4).

The MMBB-MB was implemented using original and customized functions from jsPsych (De Leeuw, 2015), a library widely used for developing online psychological experiments. For the Movement sub-battery, we developed an original extension that captures device motion data (i.e., accelerometer and gyroscope signals) and integrates these measurements with other jsPsych plugins. This extension was later contributed back to the library as open-source software (Neto,

2021). For server-side operations and database management, we used JATOS (Lange et al., 2021). Our codebase, openly available in our git repository (Neto, Kauramäki, & Mavrolampados, 2021), was designed to maximize compatibility across browsers and hardware platforms while remaining modular, flexible, and easily customizable. Researchers can selectively include or exclude sub-batteries, modify stimuli and task parameters, add new components, and create tailored versions for different age groups and target populations.

3. Rhythm task

a. Tapping

In classic tapping tasks (e.g. Dunlap, 1910; Cameron, 2015; Jin, 2019; Georgi, 2023), individuals are required to infer the phase and the periodicity of the beat from an auditory stimulus, and tap on a flat surface along with that perceived beat. In our implementation, there are three trials: unpaced, metronome, and music tapping (Table 1). In the first, individuals are asked to tap at a tempo of their preference, in the absence of external auditory stimuli. Unpaced tapping allows us to evaluate internal timing mechanisms, as well as the individual's preferred beat rate, which has been shown to differ across lifespan (McAuley, 2006).

For the second and third trials, respectively, a metronome and a musical stimulus are presented. Individuals are asked to tap along with the perceived beat of these stimuli. Following the design of the BAASTA (Dalla Bella, 2017), each stimulus was shifted to 80, 100 and 133 Beats Per Minute (BPM). Six versions were created for each trial, one for each possible sequence of BPM changes. Tempo shifts occur at every 33.3 beats, and each participant is randomly assigned to one out of the six versions. Besides enabling the evaluation of basic sensory-motor synchronization skills (described in further detail in section 3.b), tempo changes allow us to measure the accuracy and the speed at which individuals can adapt to sudden changes in the beat periodicity. Tempo manipulation was performed using the TSM toolbox for MATLAB, specifically by applying the *élastique* Pro V3 algorithm hosted in sonicAPI (Driedger, 2013).

FIGURE 2 - Display of beat alignment and tapping tasks. Letters a, b, c and d are displayed here as examples to the connection between a button and the corresponding offset between beat (peaks of soundwave) and metronome (vertical lines). When the users click one of the buttons on the screen, they hear a corresponding alignment between beat and metronome. These letters are not visible to participants during the task.

b. Beat Alignment

The **Beat Alignment Task** (BAT) is based on previous paradigms (Harrison & Müllensiefen, 2018; Dalla Bella, 2017; Fujii & Schlaug, 2013; Iversen & Patel, 2010), where a musical stimulus and a metronome are presented concomitantly, with varying levels of phase shift between them. Participants are usually given a two-alternative forced choice task (2AFC), and have to indicate whether or not the beat and the metronome are aligned.

In our version of the BAT, instead of the 2AFC, participants are asked to manipulate the phase of a metronome until it is aligned with the beat of a looped musical stimulus. The metronome is presented at offsets from one to eight demisemiquavers, considering the crotchet as one beat. Ideal responses would be achieved if the participant chose an offset of zero or four demisemiquavers between metronome and beat, which correspond to the downbeat and to the upbeat of the stimulus, respectively.

Manipulation of the metronome occurs by pressing buttons that are displayed circularly on the screen of the phone (Figure 2). Each button increases the offset of the metronome clockwise by one demisemiquaver. Offset zero is placed randomly throughout one of the eight buttons, and the initial offset is never zero or four (Figure 2a and 2c), in order for the trials not to start in perfect phase or counter phase conditions.

With this version of the BAT, we created a beat production task which does not require highly complex sensory-motor synchronization skills as other beat production paradigms, but still allows for a fine-grained evaluation of beat perception. Rather than showing many trials with different offsets between beat and metronome, our task shows all alignment possibilities in one trial, and individuals indicate which one they perceive as the most well aligned. While traditional BAT forces individuals to choose between two beat alignments, every trial of our task shows 8 alternative beat alignments, which arguably reduces the probability of individuals making correct random guesses.

c. Stimulus selection

In the first two trials of the tapping task (Table 1) participants were presented with silence (unpaced tapping) and a metronome. In the third trial, participants were asked to tap along with El Pesebre, chosen for its low familiarity, stable tempo, and clear, danceable rhythm. The recording also permits tempo manipulation without major perceptual distortion, allowing experimental flexibility. The stimulus selection of BAT started with an initial sample of 2 million tracks and 300 thousand artists taken from Spotify's Million-Playlist Dataset (Cheng, 2018). Each track is described according to pre-computed audio features, such as valence, energy, loudness, tempo and instrumentalness. First, we selected all songs with a tempo of roughly 80, 100, and 133 BPM, allowing for a deviation of plus or minus 5 BPM. In order to select songs without lyrics, tracks with instrumentalness below the third quartile were excluded.

Finally, targeting songs with varying levels of danceability and energy, we proposed the Summed Energy and Danceability (SED) score, which simply summed these two features for each song. The score was then used to categorize songs as high or low SED, corresponding to upper and lower quartiles of all scores in our sample. This selection criteria still yielded a large set of 260.000 tracks, so the final stimuli went through an extensive manual selection of six songs, one for each combination of SED and tempo (selected stimuli are available as supplementary materials).

d. Derived metrics

The tapping task collects raw tapping data in the form of tap onset times (ms), while the BAT collects the chosen temporal offset between the stimulus and the beat (measured in number

of demisemiquavers), and the number of offset adjustments attempted before a final response is given. From these data, a set of derived metrics is computed to capture complementary aspects of temporal accuracy, stability, and sensorimotor synchronization (Table 2). Unless otherwise specified, metrics can be computed at the trial level or aggregated at the participant level.

Table 2 - Individual description of metrics derived from BAT and tapping tasks.

Metric	Task	Description	Unit / Scale
Tempo accuracy	Tapping	Difference between tapping and stimulus tempo	BPMs
Tapping variability	Tapping	Stability of inter-tap intervals	BPMs
Tapping drift	Tapping	Measurement of increases or decreases in inter-tap interval throughout the trial	BPMs
Phase synchrony	Tapping	Temporal alignment between taps and stimulus beat	0–1
Period confidence	Tapping	Strength of tapping periodicity	0–1
Offset	BAT	Number of demisemiquavers between stimulus and chosen beat	0-7
Processing time	BAT	Time it takes for participant to find the final offset between stimulus and beat	ms

4. Movement task

The movement sub-battery is designed to quantify internal timing mechanisms, as well as sensory-motor synchronization skills. Similar to the tapping task, the movement sub-battery consists of three components: unpaced walking, bouncing to metronome, and free dance to music. First, participants are asked to walk around at a speed that feels most comfortable to them, and no auditory stimulus is presented. As with unpaced tapping, the periodicity of spontaneous walking is affected by age (Bohannon, 1997), and it is an indication of internal timing mechanisms.

For the second trial, participants are asked to bounce in synchrony with the beat of a metronome. The third component consists of two trials, one with a stimulus pre-defined by the researcher, and the other chosen by the participant amongst a pool of 6 different songs. In both trials, participants are asked to dance freely to the music. As with the tapping task, the tempo of each stimulus was shifted to 80, 100 and 133 BPMs, and six versions were created, one for each possible order of BPM change. Again, tempo shifts occurred at every 33.3 beats, and each participant was randomly assigned to one of the six versions. Tempo manipulations were performed using the same algorithms described for the tapping task.

In this sub-battery, we take advantage of the fact that modern mobile phones are almost always equipped with sensors such as accelerometer and gyroscope, and all our tasks can be performed remotely. This allows individuals to perform complex movement patterns, which offers a more complete view of sensory-motor synchronization skills. For instance, participants may embody distinct metric levels at the same time (Toiviainen, 2010), or within different axes of the Euclidean three dimensional space (Hartmann, 2019), which is not possible to capture with simple finger tapping tasks.

a. Stimulus selection

Similar to the tapping task, the first 3 trials of the movement task presented individuals with silence (unpaced walking), a metronome (bouncing) and El Pesebre (free dance). The 6 songs used in the self-selected trial were also derived from the Million-Playlist Dataset (Cheng, 2018), with the same filtering strategy as the one used in the tapping task, except that only songs with high SED scores were chosen. Figure 3 shows the interface where individuals could click on each song button, listen to samples of each song, and choose the one that they would like to dance to.

b. Derived metrics

The Movement sub-battery collects raw kinematic data in the form of linear acceleration (accelerometer; m/s^2) and angular velocity (gyroscope; rad/s). From these signals, a set of derived metrics (Table 3) is computed to characterize the magnitude, structure, and temporal organization of body movement in response to musical stimuli. The raw data are used to quantify complementary aspects of movement intensity, coordination, periodicity, and stability. Unless otherwise specified, each metric is computed at the trial level and subsequently aggregated at the participant level.

FIGURE 3 Stimulus selection for free-movement task.

Table 3 - Individual description of metrics derived from the accelerometer of movement tasks.

Metric	Description	Unit / Scale
Effective dimensionality	Distribution of movement patterns across 3-dimensional space	0-3
RMS	Overall amount of movement	m/s ²
Phase synchrony	Temporal alignment between movement and beat	0-1
Period confidence	Stability of dominant movement period	0-1
Proportion of synchronized power	Power distribution across 3 metric levels (original, half and double tempo)	0-100% per metric level
Tempo error	Difference between performed tempo and original tempo	0-∞

5. Emotion

Emotion recognition (ER) in music has been studied extensively in recent decades. Research topics have looked at the underlying cognitive mechanisms of decoding musical emotions (Juslin & Västfjäll, 2008), individual differences (MacGregor et al., 2023), universalities vs. cultural specificities (Fritz et al., 2009), influence of acoustic features (e.g. mode, rhythm, timbre, Eerola et al., 2009), and correlates with cognitive abilities (Nordström & Laukka, 2019), psychometric traits (Akkermans et al., 2019), and demographics (Hunter et al., 2010). Measurement typically involves forced-choice trials of emotion classification, rating scales, or free-text descriptions.

General emotion research has produced plenty of psychometric tests to assess the ability to process emotion-related information, often referred to as emotion recognition ability (ERA; e.g. ERI, Scherer & Scherer, 2011; ERAM, Laukka et al., 2021). A few similar attempts have been made to measure the ability to recognise emotions in music (musical ERA; MacGregor et al., 2023), although these employed non-naturalistic (experimentally manipulated) audio excerpts, raising some concerns for ecological validity. Despite these recent developments, researchers still rely on crude estimations rather than validated instruments, limiting precision and comparability between studies. Other challenges include the selection of appropriate music excerpts (using validated stimuli) and test duration (ER tasks are often long and susceptible to biases such as participant fatigue). Overall, the field still lacks the level of systematisation required for robust psychometric assessment. To address these issues, we developed two short emotions subbatteries.

a. Short Musical Affect Recognition Test (SMART)

The Short Musical Affect Recognition Test (SMART; Mavrolampados et al., 2026) is an adaptive musical ERA test, the first in the field to use naturalistic excerpts. It uses a standard two-alternative forced choice (2AFC) task. Participants listen to a 10-second film music excerpt and are presented with two emotion labels. They are then asked ‘Which of these two emotions does the music express the most?’. There are five discrete emotions in the test (Anger, Fear, Happiness, Tenderness, Sadness), chosen for their wide use and salience in previous studies (for a review, see Warrenburgh, 2019). The test has 20 trials, applies emotion stratification to ensure each term equally contributes to the final score (4 trials per emotion), and takes approximately five minutes to complete. The test outcome is a score denoting the test-taker’s ability to decode emotions in music. A test screenshot for mobile devices can be seen in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4 Example of SMART trial interface. While the excerpt is playing, emotion options appear faded and cannot be selected.

An important methodological aspect of SMART is the use of Computerised Adaptive Testing (CAT; van der Linden & Glas, 2000; Wainer et al., 2000). The approach adjusts the test's difficulty to the ability level of the test-taker. Thus, every test run involves a different set of encountered items. CAT has several advantages, including drastic reduction in test duration (participants only encounter relevant items, maximising information), generalisability/fairness (the test is sensitive to an expanded ability range, making it suitable for more diverse groups), and increased validity and reliability (better methods for scoring and reliability assessment). Participant ability estimation is calculated through a Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MLE), and the next item selection is operationalised by an information function (for more information, see Mavrolampados et al., 2026). The test has a large item bank of 544 candidate items, allowing it to accommodate participants of diverse abilities. Construct validity results showed positive correlations between SMART's score and ERA's in other modalities (vocal, facial), general musical skills, and negative correlations with alexithymia. Reliability results revealed good reliability for approximately 15 trials or more, sensitivity to a wide range of abilities, and robustness to key demographics.

b. Perception of Affect in Music (PAM)

While the second emotion subbattery does not concern ER ability per se, it measures subjective emotion perception through a dimensional model and enjoyment. Following discrete emotion models, dimensional approaches are the second-most frequently used in music research (Eerola & Vuoskoski, 2013). As in traditional models (e.g. Russell, 1980), our dimensional model is based on valence and arousal. Enjoyment, on the other hand, is measured through one single slider. The outcomes of this subbattery are the ratings the participants gave to valence, arousal, and liking. These can be used to measure, for example, biases towards negativity / positivity (tendency to rate valence more negative / positive), arousal sensitivity (high variability in the arousal ratings), emotional flexibility (high overall variability), and preferences.

Fifteen (15) film music excerpts are presented in a randomised order. Each excerpt is a representative of the five discrete emotions mentioned above and one high, middle, and low example per emotion was chosen using the mean ratings provided in Eerola & Vuoskoski (2011). Participants listen to each excerpt and provide ratings of valence (labels: Very negative, Very positive) and arousal (labels: Very low energy, Very high energy), and liking (how much they like the excerpts, labels Not at all, Very much). A continuous slider (0-100) collects responses for all ratings and visual cues in the form of emojis are used in the scale extremes (Figure 5). Participants can replay the excerpt as many times as they wish before making an evaluation.

FIGURE 5 Example of test interface with excerpt playing and ratings for valence, arousal, and preference. Screens appeared in order from left to right.

c. Stimulus selection

Both emotion sub-batteries use stimuli from the Film Music Stimulus Set (FMSS; Eerola & Vuoskoski, 2011), a dataset of 110 instrumental film music excerpts rated along five discrete emotions (Anger, Fear, Happiness, Tenderness, Sadness), and three dimensions (Valence, Arousal, Tension). Excerpts are naturalistic (non-constrained) and include several musical styles of instrumental music. We selected FMSS as it has been shown to be implicitly familiar to a wide audience due to the global exposure of film music, thus enhancing generalisability. It can also minimise extramusical associations in terms of familiarity, as participants are normally familiar with the music style, but not the music itself (e.g. they cannot name the tracks or artists). Most importantly, it is one of the most validated datasets on the field, with replications in different countries and languages that confirmed cross-cultural consistency and the high quality of its excerpts (e.g. Fuentes-Sanchez et al., 2021; Nineuil, Dellacherie, & Samson, 2022; Merrill et al., 2020). Ratings from the initial study (Eerola & Vuoskoski, 2011) and a recent Spanish replication (Fuentes-Sanchez et al., 2021) were used in both subbatteries (N = 243).

d. Derived metrics

The emotion sub-batteries collect three types of raw data: visual analog scale ratings, button presses in an 2 Alternative Forced Choice Task (2AFCT), and time taken for the participants to give their ratings. These raw values are used to calculate SMART and PAM. These metrics are described in further detail in Table 4.

Table 4 - Individual description of metrics derived from emotion sub-batteries.

Metric	Task	Description	Unit / Scale
SMART score	Emotion recognition (2AFC)	Final ability test score, computed through Maximum Likelihood Estimation from all participant's responses	[-6:6], continuous
PAM	Emotion ratings	Average valence, arousal, liking ratings across all excerpts	1-100
PAM	Emotion ratings	Average valence, arousal, liking ratings across per emotion (Anger, Fear, Happiness, Tenderness, Sadness)	1-100

6. Singing task

Singing entails the vocal production of musical tones either with or without words, involving a number of auditory and vocal-motor abilities, such as perception and vocal production of pitch and rhythm, breath control, vocal range, tone quality, and articulation, as well as linguistic processing. Singing is commonly assessed with tasks involving vocal production of individual tones, tone sequences (melodies), and/or songs, either spontaneously, after hearing an auditory model, or along an auditory model. The custom-made singing task (duration: 10 min) of the MMBB-MB comprises 4 subtests assessing these domains.

FIGURE 6. Singing sub-battery interface.

In the beginning of the task, there is a short **vocal warm-up phase**, which entails also selecting the vocal range for the task. The subjects hear a familiar song (*Happy Birthday*, duration 17 sec) sung by a male / female singer from 3 vocal ranges each spanning an octave: low (male: E2-E3 / female: E3-E4), mid (male: A2-A3 / female: G3-G4), and high (male: E3-E4 / female: E4-E5). These particular vocal ranges were selected as they correspond to the ranges in which most people without singing training find it comfortable to sing from. For children, the female vocal ranges are used. While listening, the subjects are asked to sing along, and after this, they are asked to choose the vocal range that felt most comfortable for them to sing in. The selected vocal range is then used in all the following 4 subtests.

Subtest 1 involves **singing single tones** (duration: 1 sec) from the Happy Birthday melody (all tones within one octave). The subtest comprises two parts. In part A, subjects hear a single tone sung on syllable /la/, and their task is to sing it back right after hearing (8 trials). In part B, subjects hear a single tone sung on syllable /la/ two times, and their task is to listen on the first time and sing along to the sung model on the second time (8 trials). Both parts are preceded by a single practice trial. The presentation order of parts A and B is randomized.

Subtest 2 involves **singing short tone sequences** (3-5 tones, duration: 2-3 sec) from the Happy Birthday (50%) and novel song (50%) melodies (all tones within one octave). Half of the tone sequences have no rhythmic pattern (all 1/4 notes) and half have a rhythmic pattern (combination of 1/2, 1/4 and 1/8 notes). The subtest comprises two parts. In part A, subjects hear a tone sequence sung on syllable /la/, and their task is to sing it back right after hearing (10 trials). In part B, subjects hear a tone sequence sung on syllable /la/ two times, and their task is to listen on the first time and sing along to the sung model on the second time (10 trials). Both parts are preceded by a single practice trial. The presentation order of parts A and B is randomized.

Subtest 3 involves **singing a familiar song** (*Happy Birthday*, sung to a person called Hannah, lyrics shown on screen, duration: 17 sec). The subtest comprises two parts. In part A, the task is to sing the song once from memory (without a model). In part B, the task is to sing the song once along with a sung model. The presentation order of parts A and B is randomized. In part A, the purpose is not to test how well subjects recall the song melody but how well they are able to produce it by themselves. To facilitate this, the subjects have heard the song already three times in the warm-up phase (and once in part B, if it came before part A in randomization).

Subtest 4 involves **learning to sing a novel song** (*Do you know what time it is?*, duration: 17 sec), which is composed from the same tones as the *Happy Birthday* melody and has novel lyrics corresponding in linguistic complexity and word length with *Happy Birthday*. The subtest starts with an introductory round in which subjects hear the song and see its lyrics on screen once, and they are asked to focus on listening and not to sing along. In the following test phase, subjects hear the song and see its lyrics on screen three times, and their task is to sing along to the sung model.

In subtests 1-4, subjects are also asked to rate on a 5-point scale after each subtest part how easy/difficult the task felt (Figure 6), in order to explore how objective task performance is linked to subjective experience. Overall, the design of the singing task enables direct comparison of (i) tone-, sequence-, and song-level vocal production using the same set of tones within an octave range, sung from the vocal range most comfortable for the subject; (ii) solo and unison singing; and (iii) singing of familiar vs. novel songs as well as (iv) exploring song learning. Coupled with short overall duration (10 min) and simple instructions, this makes the task applicable for use with both healthy adults and children as well as for clinical populations (e.g., aphasic stroke patients, persons with dementia).

a. Derived metrics

Raw audio data is stored, and used to extract measures of pitch and temporal accuracy (supplementary material). The resulting performance metrics are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5 - Individual description of metrics derived from singing sub-batteries.

Metric	Task	Description	Unit / Scale
Pitch Error	Singing single tones, short tone sequences, familiar song and novel song	Amplitude-weighted mean absolute difference between instantaneous participant pitch and expected pitch (template), computed in semitones.	Semitones
Detrended Pitch Error	Singing short tone sequences, familiar song and novel song	Same as Pitch Error but computed after removing slow pitch trends to account for gradual drift from key.	Semitones
Pitch Direction Error	Singing short tone sequences, familiar song and novel song	Compares Parsons-code-like directional patterns (ascent/descent) of successive segments between participant and template, summing absolute directional differences.	Unitless (absolute directional difference count)
Relational Pitch Error	Singing short tone sequences, familiar song and novel song	Compares magnitudes of inter-segment intervals between participant and template instead of just direction.	Semitones (interval magnitude difference)
Rhythm Error	Singing short tone sequences, familiar song and novel song	Rhythm error reflects the degree of temporal stretching or compression required to align a participant's performance with the reference timing, such that larger adjustments indicate greater rhythmic deviation.	Normalized temporal warping cost (unitless)

7. Perception & Memory task

A core musical ability is to be able to perceive spectral (pitch) and temporal (rhythm) features in new melodies we hear and to form memory representations of the melodies, enabling their recognition. The Perception & Memory part of the MMBB-MB consists of the Melody, Rhythm, and Memory subtests from the abbreviated Montreal Battery for Evaluation of Musical Abilities (MBEMA) (Peretz et al., 2013). Adapted from the widely used Montreal Battery of

Evaluation of Amusia (MBEA; Peretz et al., 2003), the MBEMA is applicable across cultures and for a wider range of participants, including small children as well as clinical populations, due to its relatively short length (20 min). The music stimuli in MBEMA comprise 20 short unfamiliar tonal melodies, which are 5-9 tones long and played in 10 different keys (half major, half minor) and with different instrument timbres.

The Melody and Rhythm subtests include 20 trials with a target melody and a comparison melody separated by a 1.5-s silent interval. In half of the trials, the target and comparison melodies are identical and in half the comparison melody contains either a melodic change (scale, contour, or interval violation of 2-5 semitones) or a rhythmic change (changing the durations of two adjacent tones to alter the rhythmic grouping of notes), respectively. The serial position of the changes varies across melodies. The task of the subjects is to judge, on each trial, whether the target and comparison melodies are the same or different. The Memory subtest is presented last and includes 20 trials, half of which have old melodies heard earlier in the session (in the Melody and Rhythm subtests) and half of which have new melodies (similar sounding as the old melodies but differing in their exact temporal and pitch patterns). The task of the subjects is to judge, on each trial, if they recognize the melody from earlier in the session (yes/no). The 20 trials in each subtest are preceded by two practice trials.

a. Derived metrics

The raw data of MBEMA consists of 1 and 0, indicating whether the response given was correct or incorrect, respectively. Overall scores are calculated as the percentage of correct responses given by participants.

Table 66 - Individual description of metrics derived from Perception & memory tasks.

Metric	Task	Description	Unit / Scale
Melody	2AFC task	Percentage of correct responses given to melody trials	0-1
Memory	2AFC task	Percentage of correct responses given to Memory trials	0-1
Rhythm	2AFC task	Percentage of correct responses given to rhythm trials	0-1

8. Music Experience

In addition to our objectively measured ability to perceive music, move to music, sing, and recognize and experience emotions from music, an important domain of music cognition is our subjective experience of music in daily life. The Music Experience part of the MMBB-MB provides a selection of standardized questionnaires (70 items in total, duration: 10 min) measuring music background, genre preferences, reward value of music, use of music in mood regulation, and different musical skills.

a. Questionnaires

Music background is measured with 8 items on length of hobby experience and training (outside of primary/lower secondary school) in singing, instrument playing, and dancing (5-point scale: never – more than 10 years), frequency of current music listening (5-point scale: never – daily), and overall evaluation of musicality (5-point scale: not at all musical – very musical).

Genre preference is measured with 13 items from the Short Test of Music Preferences (STOMP; Rentfrow & Gosling, 2003) in which subjects are asked to rate their liking of 13 different music genres (blues, jazz, classical, folk, rock, alternative, heavy metal, country, religious, pop, rap/hip-hop, soul/funk, electronic/dance) on a 7-point scale (dislike strongly – like strongly).

Music reward is measured with 20 items from the Barcelona Music Reward Questionnaire (BMRQ; Mas-Herrero et al., 2013) in which subjects are asked to express their view on statements regarding 5 domains of music reward (musical seeking, emotion evocation, mood regulation, social reward, and sensory-motor) on a 5-point scale (completely disagree – completely agree).

Use of music in mood regulation is measured with 14 items from the Brief Music in Mood Regulation (B-MMR; Saarikallio, 2012) in which subjects are asked to express their view on statements regarding use of music in 7 domains of mood regulation (entertainment, revival, strong sensation, diversion, discharge, mental work, and solace) on a 5-point scale (completely disagree – completely agree).

Subjective musical skills are measured with 15 items from the Goldsmiths Musical Sophistication Index (Gold-MSI, Müllensiefen et al., 2014) and the Goldsmiths Dance Sophistication Index (Gold-DSI; Rose et al., 2022) in which subjects are asked to express their

view on statements regarding their ability to perceive music (Gold-MSI: 5 items), sing (Gold-MSI: 5 items), and dance (Gold-MDI: 5 items). Essentially, these items were selected to provide a subjective view of the domains assessed in the Perception & Memory, Singing, and Rhythm & Movement tasks of the MMBB-MB.

Generally, these questionnaires were chosen because of their cultural versatility, wide adoptance in the literature, as well as their satisfactory psychometric properties (e.g., Gouveia et al., 2008; Saliba et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2023; Mas-Herrero et al., 2013; Saarikallio, 2012; Ansani et al., 2023; Müllensiefen et al., 2014; Lima et al., 2020; Rose et al., 2022).

b. Derived metrics

Music experience is operationalized as a set of scores derived from multiple questionnaires. With the exception of the Music Background measure, all questionnaires transform raw Likert-scale responses into a set of factors representing specific music-related constructs. These factors are listed in Table 7; however, further details regarding their computation and theoretical interpretation can be found in the original publications associated with each questionnaire, as cited in the preceding section.

Table 7 - Individual description of metrics derived from the music experience sub-batteries.

Metric	Task	Description	Unit / Scale
Music background scores	Likert scale ratings	Individual scores for each question. General music background score can be calculated as the average of all eight items.	1-5
Genre preference	STOMP Likert scale ratings	Stomp scores describe musical taste according to 5 factors: Energetic & Rhythmic; Intense & Rebellious; Reflective & Complex; Upbeat & Conventional. Participant responses are converted to one score for each of these factors.	0-7
Music reward	BMRQ likert scale responses	BMRQ scores describe musical rewards according to 5 factors: Emotion evocation, Mood regulation, Sensory motor, Social reward and Overall score.	0-100
Use of music in mood regulation	B-MMR likert scale responses	B-MMR scores describe the use of music in mood regulation according to 5 factors:	0-5

Metric	Task	Description	Unit / Scale
		Revival; Strong sensation; Diversion; Discharge; Mental work and Solace.	
Subjective musical skills	Gold-MSI and Gold-DSI likert scale responses	Gold-MSI and Gold-DSI scores are thematically grouped into Perception, Singing, and Dancing domains. Scores for each domain are calculated as the sum of responses to questionnaire items associated with the corresponding construct.	1-7

9. Discussion

a. General accomplishments and limitations

The MMBB-MB was developed to address a longstanding fragmentation in the measurement of musicality. Whereas existing instruments have tended to isolate individual facets of music cognition (e.g., melodic perception, rhythmic processing and emotional responses), within narrow age ranges or specific clinical groups, the present battery integrates auditory, motor, cognitive, emotional, and social domains within a single framework that spans the lifespan and is applicable to both healthy and clinical populations. By enabling these domains to be assessed concurrently, the battery makes it possible to investigate relationships that have previously been difficult to examine, such as the covariation between rhythmic perception and motor synchronization, or between emotional responsiveness and social engagement with music. Its online architecture further extends the contexts in which such questions can be addressed, while remaining compatible with controlled laboratory protocols incorporating motion capture and electroencephalography (EEG).

Although the present version was implemented with a specific set of Western stimuli, the rationale for song selection and the principles governing stimulus construction have been articulated explicitly. This transparency is intended to facilitate the development of alternative versions drawing on culturally specific repertoires. The structure of the tasks is not inherently tied to Western music; the current stimuli represent one instantiation of a more general design. Researchers working in other cultural contexts may therefore adapt the battery using locally relevant materials while preserving its underlying logic.

Second, the online implementation increases both accessibility and scalability. Because the battery can be administered remotely, it affords the practical possibility of large-scale, cross-cultural data collection, including in regions that have historically been underrepresented in psychological research. This does not in itself eliminate possible bias that characterizes much of the psychological research (Henrich et al., 2010; Jacoby et al., 2020), but it lowers the logistical barriers that have traditionally reinforced it.

We do not, however, claim that the MMBB-MB is culturally universal. It is more appropriately understood as a modular and extensible framework with the potential to be adapted across contexts. Realizing this potential will require systematic cross-cultural validation, collaborative development with researchers embedded in different musical traditions, and careful examination of measurement invariance across populations.

b. Validation

The claims that can presently be made about what the MMBB-MB measures are necessarily provisional, pending a rigorous program of psychometric validation. This program will entail systematic evaluation of the reliability and construct validity of each sub-battery, comprising reliability (e.g., internal consistency, test–retest reliability) and construct validity (e.g., convergent, discriminant, and factorial validity) of each sub-battery. The latent structure of the battery will be examined using exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis, and measurement invariance will be tested across developmental stages, cultural contexts, and clinical versus non-clinical samples. Validation of the Movement sub-battery will additionally involve concurrent comparison of smartphone accelerometer data against motion capture measurements.

c. Declarations

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